

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D1.2

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DATABASE

Summary:

This deliverable documents the publication of the CRM-geothermal database, integrating literature-based and newly generated datasets, and making them openly available through a FAIR-compliant, interoperable, and sustainable online platform that underpins the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas.

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Funded by
the European Union

Title:	CRM-geothermal database		
Lead beneficiary:	University of Miskolc		
Other beneficiaries:	GFZ, IZTECH, UKRI-BGS, UoI, UNES, HI, GEL		
Due date:	30 September 2025		
Nature:	Public		
Diffusion:	all Partners		
Status:	Working Document		
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.18623645		
License information:	CC-BY-4.0		
Recommended Citation:	Seres, A., & Hartai, É. (2026). The Horizon Europe CRM-geothermal project: Deliverable 1.2 CRM-geothermal database. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623645		
Related Data:	Seres, Anna; Hartai, Éva; Kieling, Katrin; Regenspurg, Simona (2026): CRM-geothermal Database: Geoscientific and Geochemical Data on Geothermal Systems, with Emphasis on Fluids and Critical Raw Materials in Europe and Eastern Africa. GFZ Data Services. https://doi.org/10.5880/fidgeo.2026.012 Online Fluid Atlas tool: https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu/		
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Document code:	D.1.2_CRM-geothermal		
Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 0.1	Anna Seres	23.09.2025	Working document.
Version 0.2	Anna Seres	25.09.2025	A few minor corrections and finalisation of the document.
Version 1	Anna Seres	30.04.2026	Minor revisions and inclusion of reference to the data publication

Approval status			
	Name	Function	Date
Deliverable responsible	Anna Seres	WP leader	30.04.2026
WP leader	Anna Seres	WP leader	30.04.2026
Project Coordinator	Katrin Kieling	Project manager	30.04.2026

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The CRM-geothermal project investigates the potential for the combined use of geothermal energy and the recovery of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) from geothermal systems. A cornerstone of this effort is the CRM-geothermal database, which provides a consolidated, harmonised, and openly accessible repository of information on the occurrence and behaviour of CRMs and associated elements in geothermal environments across Europe and East Africa.

This deliverable builds upon Deliverable 1.1 by advancing from data collection to data publication. It documents the process of making the CRM-geothermal database publicly available, ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and adopting international standards for metadata and licensing.

The published database integrates two complementary categories of data:

- Existing data, gathered from scientific literature, reports, and legacy project databases (REFLECT, PERFORM), as described in D1.1 (Seres et al. 2024). These datasets provide an essential baseline of knowledge, spanning a wide geographic range and covering diverse geothermal environments.
- New data, generated during the implementation of the project through systematic sampling and analysis of geothermal fluids, rocks, scales, and gases in selected sites across Europe and East Africa. These include chemical analyses, mineralogical characterisations, and experimental leaching studies, which enrich the database with high-quality, up-to-date measurements.

Data collection within CRM-geothermal is a continuous process throughout the project lifetime. Newly created data are regularly validated, harmonised, and integrated into the CRM-geothermal database, ensuring that the published resource is dynamic, progressively expanding, and constantly improving in quality and coverage. The database is accessible through the dedicated online platform (<https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu/>), which provides search, filter, and visualisation functionalities, and allows users to download the whole database or selected datasets. The status of the database as of April 2026 is published in a data publication: Seres, Anna; Hartai, Éva; Kieling, Katrin; Regenspurg, Simona (2026): CRM-geothermal Database: Geoscientific and Geochemical Data on Geothermal Systems, with Emphasis on Fluids and Critical Raw Materials in Europe and Eastern Africa. GFZ Data Services. <https://doi.org/10.5880/fidgeo.2026.012>. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) and an open access license (CC-BY 4.0) ensure that the datasets can be properly cited, reused, and preserved beyond the lifetime of the project.

The publication of the CRM-geothermal database marks a significant milestone: it transforms a heterogeneous collection of legacy and newly generated datasets into a coherent, transparent, and sustainable resource. This database serves as the foundation for the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and will support ongoing scientific research, industrial innovation, and policy-making on the sustainable co-production of heat and critical raw materials.

2 INTRODUCTION

Geothermal systems are increasingly recognised not only as a renewable energy source but also as potential providers of strategic raw materials including CRMs, which are essential for the EU's green and digital transition. Co-production of heat and CRMs from geothermal reservoirs could contribute to the diversification of supply, improved resource efficiency, and reduced dependency on imported raw materials. To explore this potential, the CRM-geothermal project has established a database as a central instrument for consolidating, analysing, and publishing relevant data.

Deliverable 1.1 presented the methodology and results of the collection of existing data, drawn from scientific literature, technical reports, and legacy projects such as REFLECT and PERFORM (Seres et al.2024). This work created the foundation of the database by integrating heterogeneous datasets into a harmonised and quality-checked structure, covering a wide range of geothermal environments in Europe and East Africa.

In addition to the formerly existing data, the project has also generated new data through systematic sampling and analysis of geothermal fluids, gases, scales, and rocks in selected sites. These efforts provided high-quality geochemical and mineralogical information, including results from field sampling campaigns and laboratory experiments, which significantly enriched the database.

Data collection in CRM-geothermal is a continuous process throughout the project lifetime. As new results become available, they are progressively validated, harmonised, and added to the database, ensuring that the published resource is dynamic and up to date. This continuous enrichment guarantees that the CRM-geothermal database will remain a reliable and comprehensive knowledge base for the duration of the project and beyond.

The present deliverable represents the transition from data collection to data publication. Its objectives are:

- To make the CRM-geothermal database openly available in accordance with the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
- To describe the integration of both literature-based and newly generated data into a single, harmonised resource.
- To document the technical implementation of the publication platform, metadata standards, and licensing.
- To establish a framework for continuous updating and long-term sustainability of the published data.

By publishing the CRM-geothermal database, the project ensures that collected and newly created data are accessible to a wide range of stakeholders, including scientists, industry actors, and policymakers. Moreover, the database forms the backbone of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas, which will provide interactive visualisation and support further research, exploration, and innovation in the sustainable use of geothermal resources for CRM recovery.

3 PRINCIPLES AND STANDARDS FOR DATA PUBLICATION

The publication of the CRM-geothermal database follows established best practices for scientific data management to ensure transparency, usability, and long-term value. In line with European Commission requirements for Horizon Europe projects, the database has been designed and published according to widely recognised principles and standards. These ensure that the datasets are not only made available but also structured and documented in a way that maximises their scientific, industrial, and societal impact.

To achieve this, the publication approach is structured around four core dimensions — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) — supported by the use of international metadata standards and open access licensing practices.

3.1 FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES

The CRM-geothermal database has been developed and published in accordance with the FAIR data principles, ensuring that the information collected within the project is not only preserved but also openly available and usable by a wide range of stakeholders. Applying the FAIR principles is essential to maximise the impact of the data, facilitate reuse across scientific and industrial domains, and ensure long-term sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project. The application of each FAIR principle is described in detail in Table 1, outlining how these concepts have been implemented within the CRM-geothermal database.

Table 1: FAIR compliance matrix of the CRM-geothermal database.

FAIR principle	Implementation in CRM-geothermal
Findable	A persistent identifier (DOI) is assigned to the data publication of the CRM-geothermal database, ensuring findability and citability. Rich metadata records allow discovery via search engines and data catalogues. The online platform supports keyword and advanced search with filters by site, sample type, or element.
Accessible	The database is openly available at https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu/ . Access is granted under a CC-BY 4.0 license. Secure access protocols (HTTPS) ensure long-term usability.
Interoperable	Data are provided in a widely accessible Excel (XLSX) format, enabling straightforward use in common statistical, modelling, and GIS software. Metadata align with INSPIRE, EPOS, and EGDI standards, and harmonised vocabularies and units support comparability. Cross-links to other H2020 project datasets (REFLECT, PERFORM) are established.
Reusable	Detailed metadata provide provenance, methods, and references. Quality control procedures ensure reliability. Clear licensing and citation guidelines support reuse in science, industry, and policy. Compatibility with modelling, AI tools, and the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas ensures further applicability.

3.2 METADATA STANDARDS AND DOCUMENTATION

To maximise discoverability, interoperability, and reuse, the CRM-geothermal database adopts internationally recognised metadata standards. Each dataset is accompanied by structured metadata records that describe:

- Identification: title, authors/partners, date of creation, DOI, version.
- Content description: type of data (fluid, rock, gas, scale), geographic location, geothermal context, measured parameters, units.
- Methodology: sampling procedures, laboratory analysis techniques, quality checks.
- Provenance and references: original sources (for literature data) or project partners and laboratories (for newly generated data).
- Access and use conditions: license (CC-BY 4.0), recommended citation.

Metadata records are aligned with the Dublin Core and INSPIRE standards for geoscientific data, ensuring interoperability with European data infrastructures such as EGD and EPOS. Controlled vocabularies (e.g. IUGS/CGI standards for lithology and geochemistry) and harmonised units of measurement (e.g. SI system) further guarantee consistency across datasets.

The metadata schema is documented in detail in Annex 1, which provides a full list of fields, definitions, and controlled vocabularies used.

3.3 LICENSING AND OPEN ACCESS

The CRM-geothermal database is published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) license. This ensures that the data are freely accessible, and may be reused, redistributed, or adapted for any purpose, provided appropriate credit is given.

A recommended citation is provided for the CRM-geothermal data publication as a whole. Individual records include source references, with DOIs or other persistent identifiers where available, ensuring traceability to the original data sources. The data publication is assigned a DOI through GFZ Data Services, ensuring long-term accessibility, traceability, and citability.

In line with Horizon Europe open science requirements, the database is made available without restrictions to the widest possible audience, including scientific researchers, industrial actors, policymakers, and the general public.

4 DATABASE CONTENT AND DATA SOURCES

The CRM-geothermal database consolidates diverse information on the occurrence and behaviour of Critical Raw Materials (CRMs) and related elements in geothermal environments. Its content derives from two complementary sources: (1) pre-existing data collected from literature, technical reports, and legacy projects, and (2) new data generated during the project through systematic sampling and laboratory analysis. Together, these datasets provide a robust and comprehensive resource that underpins the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and supports subsequent project tasks (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Data sources and integration into the CRM-geothermal database. Existing data (literature, legacy projects) and new data (sampling and analysis) are harmonised and integrated into the CRM-geothermal database, which directly feeds into the Fluid Atlas for online visualisation and user access.

4.1 DATA CATEGORIES

The database integrates a wide range of data types relevant to geothermal systems, organised into structured categories (Table 2). These categories ensure a consistent structure across datasets, facilitating search, comparison, and integration into the Fluid Atlas.

Table 2: Overview of data categories in the CRM-geothermal database

Category	Description	Examples of parameters	Entries / Coverage
Wells	General information on geothermal wells, including geographic, geological, and operational context.	Well name, location (lat/long), depth, temperature.	~3800 wells across Europe and East Africa.
Fluids	Chemical composition of geothermal waters, with emphasis on CRM and associated elements.	Major ions (Na, K, Ca, Mg, Cl, SO ₄), trace elements (Li, Sr, Cs, Rb, REE, PGE), pH, temperature.	~4900 fluid analyses from previous projects, literature and new sampling campaigns.
Rocks	Bulk geochemistry and mineralogy of reservoir and host rocks, including experimental leaching studies.	Elemental composition (XRF, ICP-MS), mineral phases (XRD), leaching results (Li, Cu, Sr release).	~920 rock samples analysed (legacy + project-generated).
Scales / Precipitates	Solid deposits from geothermal installations, often enriched in CRMs.	Concentrations of Sr, Pb, Zn, Ag, Cs; mineralogical composition.	~60 scale samples from Turkey, Iceland, East Africa.
Gases	Composition of dissolved and free gases in geothermal systems.	CO ₂ , CH ₄ , H ₂ , N ₂ , He, noble gases.	~40 gas samples from Turkey, Cornwall, East Africa.
PGE / REE datasets	Focused data on strategic elements with specific analytical challenges.	REE distribution patterns, PGE (Pt, Pd, Rh, Ir, Ru, Os) concentrations.	144 PGE/REE analysis. Targeted analyses from field and lab samples (GFZ, partner labs).

4.2 EXISTING DATA FROM LITERATURE AND LEGACY PROJECTS

The first component of the database consists of data compiled from existing sources, as reported in Deliverable 1.1 (Seres et al. 2024). These sources include:

- Peer-reviewed scientific publications and conference proceedings.
- Technical and industrial reports on geothermal projects.
- Legacy datasets from previous Horizon 2020 projects, notably REFLECT and PERFORM.

During the collection process, particular attention was given to data harmonisation, ensuring consistent units, nomenclature, and metadata. The scope was extended beyond high-enthalpy systems to also cover lower-temperature resources (<100°C), thereby broadening the database to include a wide spectrum of geothermal environments. Geographic coverage spans Europe and East Africa, with several hundred entries on fluids, wells, and rock (Table 3).

Table 3: Number of formerly existing literature data in the CRM-geothermal database (as of August 2025)

Data source		Data category				
		Well	Fluid	Rock	Gas	Scale
Data base	REFLECT	3164	3832	439	0	0
	PERFORM	53	153	14	0	4
Articles books, reports	Cont. Europe	376	471	375	0	0
	Cornwall, UK	7	19	5	0	0
	Iceland	11	16	0	0	50
	Djibouti	31	30	0	0	0
	Kenya	72	71	15	0	0
	Ethiopia	126	164	0	0	0
	Total:	3840	4756	848	0	54

This compilation provides a valuable baseline, allowing for comparative assessments across diverse geothermal settings and supporting statistical analyses of CRM concentrations and distributions.

4.3 NEW DATA GENERATED DURING THE PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

In addition to existing data, the CRM-geothermal project has produced new, high-quality datasets through targeted field campaigns and laboratory investigations (Kieling et al. 2025). These include:

- Field sampling of fluids, gases, rocks, and precipitates from key geothermal locations in Turkey (Tuzla, Seferihisar), East Africa (Kenya, Tanzania, Malawi, Rwanda), Cornwall (UK), Iceland, and Germany (Table 4).
- Chemical analyses of fluids and solids using state-of-the-art techniques such as ICP-MS, XRF, and isotope analysis, with emphasis on lithium, strontium, rare earth elements, and other critical raw materials.
- Mineralogical characterisations of host rocks and scales, including XRD and sequential extraction analyses to identify the binding and release of CRMs.
- Experimental studies simulating fluid–rock interactions and leaching processes under geothermal conditions, providing insights into CRM mobility and long-term availability.

Table 4: Number of data generated by sampling and analysis within the project lifetime (as of August 2025)

Sampling location	Well	Fluid	Rock	Gas	Scale
Germany	0	0	23	0	0
UK	0	47	5	3	0
Iceland	To be published				
Turkey	0	23	0	6	0
Malawi	23	24	12	17	0
Tanzania	24	22	19	13	0
Rwanda	To be published				
Kenya	0	31	15	0	8
Total:	47	147	74	39	8

These new datasets significantly enhance the richness of the database, adding site-specific, validated information that complements and extends the legacy data. They also provide essential inputs for ongoing modelling, resource assessment, and technology development within the project.

4.4 DATA VALIDATION, HARMONISATION AND INTEGRATION

Both existing and newly generated datasets undergo a rigorous process of harmonisation and quality control before inclusion in the published database:

- Validation: checking consistency, plausibility, and accuracy of reported values.
 - Threshold values are set up for the water solubility of several elements, based on literature.
 - Minimum and maximum values are given for several attributes, like latitude, longitude, elevation, pH.
 - The amount of major anions and cations are checked, based on the Total Major Anion/Cation value.
 - The amount of anions and cations were validated based on anion/cation charge balance.

The first three validation steps are applied through the data submission workflow when data are uploaded via the Excel file, supporting consistency and plausibility checks. Above these, the fourth step was applied for the validation of the REFLECT database

- Harmonisation: unifying units of measurement, geochemical parameters, and terminology.
- Metadata enrichment: linking each dataset with detailed information on provenance, methods, and references.
- Integration: merging legacy and new data into a single, coherent structure that feeds directly into the Fluid Atlas.

This process ensures that all data, regardless of origin, are presented in a consistent and comparable format. It also guarantees that updates made during the project lifetime — including the continuous addition of new data — are immediately reflected in the online platform.

5 TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DATABASE PUBLICATION

The CRM-geothermal database has been made publicly accessible through a dedicated online platform, designed to ensure transparency, usability, and long-term availability of the data. The system provides a user-friendly interface for browsing, searching, and downloading datasets, while also offering robust backend functions to support continuous updates and secure data management.

In addition to the continuously updated online platform, the CRM-geothermal database is also published as a citable data publication through GFZ Data Services, with an assigned DOI representing a fixed snapshot of the dataset at the time of publication, accessible at <https://doi.org/10.5880/fidgeo.2026.012>

5.1 Conceptual overview of the CRM-geothermal data system

The CRM-geothermal data system consists of two complementary components: a continuously updated online platform and a DOI-based data publication, supported by structured metadata and detailed bibliographic references. The online platform (CRM-geothermal database and Fluid Atlas) provides dynamic access to the data, allowing users to browse, query, visualise, and download the most up-to-date version of the database. This component is continuously updated as new data are collected, validated, and integrated.

In parallel, a data publication hosted by GFZ Data Services represents a fixed, citable snapshot of the database at a given point in time. This version is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), ensuring long-term availability, reproducibility, and unambiguous citation. The database structure includes metadata fields (e.g. identifiers, location, data source, quality flags, and references), which are stored together with the data and ensure interpretability and traceability of each record.

At the level of individual entries, bibliographic references provide links to the original data sources (e.g. scientific publications, reports, or legacy databases), often including DOIs. This enables users to trace each data record back to its origin. Together, these components ensure that the CRM-geothermal database functions both as a dynamic research platform and as a stable, citable scientific data publication, fully aligned with FAIR data principles.

5.2 ONLINE PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

The database is hosted on the platform available at <https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu/> (Figure 2).

The platform has been developed to support both data collection and publication, with a seamless integration between the back-end database and the public-facing interface. A centralised data storage system ensures that updates and new data entries are automatically synchronised across the collection environment and the Fluid Atlas visualisation module.

The technical architecture is based on standard database management systems, with a web-based interface that is accessible via all major browsers. The platform supports secure access protocols (HTTPS) and has been designed with scalability and long-term maintenance in mind.

Figure 2: Visualisation map of the CRM-geothermal database.

5.3 USER ROLES AND PRIVILEGES

To balance openness with data integrity, the system implements a tiered user access structure (Table 5). Public access allows any user to browse and download the data without registration, while editing rights are restricted to prevent unintended modification or deletion. Registered users can upload new datasets and modify their own entries, but cannot alter data submitted by others. This enables broad community contribution and facilitates the incorporation of substantial new data volumes, while ensuring that the integrity and reliability of the database as a whole are preserved.

Table 5: User roles and privileges in the CRM-geothermal database

User role	Functions	Restrictions
Public user	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Browse and search datasets - View metadata - Download data in Excel format 	Cannot upload or edit any data
Registered user	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All functions of public users - Upload new datasets - Edit or delete only their own uploaded entries 	Cannot edit or delete datasets uploaded by others
Administrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full rights (all functions of registered users) - Validate and harmonise incoming data - Edit or delete any dataset - Manage user registrations and roles 	None

5.4 DATA FORMATS AND EXPORT OPTIONS

The CRM-geothermal database is accessible through both tabular and map-based interfaces. Users can explore the data online in interactive tables or through the GIS-based Fluid Atlas, which enables spatial visualisation of geothermal wells, fluid composition, and associated parameters.

For download and further analysis, datasets can be exported in Excel (XLSX) format. The exported files include both the primary data and the associated metadata fields (e.g. identifiers, source information, references, and quality-related attributes), ensuring that the data remain interpretable and traceable outside the platform.

In addition to tabular access, the Fluid Atlas provides visual outputs by allowing users to display, filter, and export map-based views of the data. These visualisations support spatial analysis and can be used for reporting and interpretation.

5.5 PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS AND CITATION

To ensure traceability and long-term availability, a snapshot of the CRM-geothermal database is published as a data publication with an assigned persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI). This DOI enables unambiguous citation and referencing of the entire dataset in scientific publications, reports, and policy documents.

Figure 3: DOI and metadata workflow for the CRM-geothermal database. The compiled dataset (including both legacy and newly generated data) is described using standardised metadata records and published as a single data publication with an assigned DOI, ensuring open access and citability.

Traceability at the level of individual data records is ensured through detailed bibliographic references included in the database. Wherever available, these references include DOIs or other persistent identifiers pointing to the original data sources (e.g. scientific publications, reports, or databases), allowing users to verify and trace each data entry back to its origin (Figure 3).

The dataset is published through GFZ Data Services and complies with Horizon Europe open science and FAIR data principles. A recommended citation format is provided to support correct attribution and reuse.

6 DATA ACCESS AND INTEROPERABILITY

The CRM-geothermal database has been designed not only as an internal project tool but as a public resource that supports scientific, industrial, and policy communities. Its publication ensures that data collected and generated within the project are findable, accessible, and reusable by a wide range of users. Interoperability with other data infrastructures guarantees that the CRM-geothermal datasets can be integrated into broader European and global knowledge bases.

6.1 DATA ACCESS VIA THE ONLINE PLATFORM

The published database is accessible through the dedicated online platform (<https://crmgeothermal.iit.uni-miskolc.hu/>). Users can:

- Perform simple and advanced searches, filtering by site, sample type, element, or parameter.
- Visualise results in the integrated Fluid Atlas, where spatial distribution can be explored on interactive maps.
- Export data in standard format (.xlsx) for further analysis.
- Download datasets together with their metadata and citation instructions.

The platform provides unrestricted access to the public under a CC-BY 4.0 license, ensuring that datasets can be freely used and cited. Registered users have the possibility to contribute new data, while administrators ensure data integrity through validation and harmonisation.

In addition to access via the online platform, the CRM-geothermal database is also available as a citable data publication through GFZ Data Services, providing a DOI-based reference to a fixed snapshot of the dataset available at <https://doi.org/10.5880/figeo.2026.01>.

6.2 CONTINUOUS UPDATES AND SYNCHRONISATION

Data collection in CRM-geothermal is a continuous process. Newly generated results from sampling campaigns, laboratory analyses, and experimental studies are progressively harmonised and added to the central database. Through the integration of the database and the Fluid Atlas, updates are synchronised in real time: once a new dataset is validated and uploaded, it becomes immediately visible in the public interface. This ensures that the database remains a dynamic and evolving resource, reflecting the most up-to-date knowledge on CRM occurrences in geothermal systems.

6.3 INTEROPERABILITY WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND INFRASTRUCTURES

The CRM-geothermal database has been developed with interoperability as a guiding principle. This is achieved by adopting international metadata standards, harmonised vocabularies, and common data formats. As a result, the database can interconnect with:

- Legacy European projects, notably REFLECT and PERFORM, whose datasets have been reviewed, harmonised, and incorporated where relevant.
- European data infrastructures such as the European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI) which ensure long-term availability and integration of geoscientific datasets.
- Other Horizon Europe initiatives and thematic portals, enabling cross-comparison of geothermal data at regional and continental scales.

The CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas acts as the primary interface for this interoperability, offering spatially visualised data and export functions that align with established European data standards (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Data access and interoperability of the CRM-geothermal database. The central CRM-geothermal database is continuously updated and directly connected to the Fluid Atlas for visualisation and user access. Interoperability with legacy projects (REFLECT, PERFORM) and European data infrastructures (EGDI, EPOS) ensures integration into the wider open data ecosystem.

6.4 ADDED VALUE OF OPEN ACCESS AND INTEROPERABILITY

By ensuring open access and interoperability, the CRM-geothermal database maximises its impact:

- Researchers can directly reuse datasets for modelling, exploration, and comparative studies.
- Industry stakeholders can access reliable geochemical and geological information to support innovation and technology development.
- Policymakers benefit from transparent, evidence-based datasets to guide strategies on raw materials and renewable energy.

In this way, the CRM-geothermal database is not an isolated project output but a contribution to a wider European open data ecosystem, supporting long-term sustainability, collaboration, and innovation.

7 DISSEMINATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

The publication of the CRM-geothermal database ensures that the knowledge generated in the project is not only preserved but also actively communicated to the widest possible audience. To maximise impact, dissemination activities are closely linked with the principles of open science, transparency, and stakeholder engagement.

7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION

The CRM-geothermal database is disseminated through multiple channels to ensure broad visibility:

- Project website (<https://crm-geothermal.eu/>) provides information, news, and direct links to the database platform.
- Fluid Atlas serves as the primary visualisation and outreach tool, making data accessible to a wide audience, including non-experts.
- GFZ Data Services is used to publish a citable data publication with an assigned DOI, representing a fixed and archivable snapshot of the CRM-geothermal database.
- Scientific conferences and workshops (e.g. EGU, Goldschmidt, SEG) are targeted for academic dissemination.

- Clustering and networking activities (e.g. Cluster Hub on raw materials for batteries) engage industrial and policy stakeholders.
- Social media and public outreach activities (as reported in WP6) promote awareness of the database and its applications.

These dissemination actions are designed to reach different stakeholder groups: researchers, geothermal operators, raw material industries, policymakers, and the general public (Table 6).

Table 6: Dissemination channels and target audiences

Channel	Description	Target audience
Project website	Main entry point for project results and database link	General public, policymakers, researchers
Fluid Atlas (online platform)	Interactive data visualisation and download	Researchers, industry, policymakers, operators
GFZ Data Services	DOI-based data publication providing a citable snapshot of the CRM-geothermal database	Academic researchers, international repositories
Scientific conferences & workshops	Presentations, posters, proceedings	Academic and industry communities
Clustering & networking activities	Joint actions with other EU projects and industrial partners	Industry, policymakers, innovation networks
Social media & public outreach	Posts, news, press releases	General public, broader stakeholder community

7.2 CONTINUOUS UPDATES

The CRM-geothermal database is not static but a dynamic resource. Data collection and integration are ongoing throughout the project:

- Legacy datasets have already been compiled and harmonised from literature and previous projects (e.g. REFLECT, PERFORM)
- New datasets from field sampling campaigns, laboratory analyses, and experimental studies are continuously validated and added.
- Real-time synchronisation ensures that updates are immediately visible in the Fluid Atlas, supporting transparency and reliability.

This process guarantees that the database remains a current and relevant resource during the project lifetime (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Continuous update cycle of the CRM-geothermal database. Data collection (legacy + new sampling) is followed by validation and harmonisation, integration into the database, publication and synchronisation with the Fluid Atlas, and reuse by stakeholders — feeding back into further data collection.

7.3 LONG-TERM SUSTAINABILITY

To ensure that the CRM-geothermal database remains available after the end of the project, sustainability measures are implemented:

- Persistent identifiers (DOIs) and open licensing (CC-BY 4.0) secure long-term accessibility and citability.
- Integration with European infrastructures such as EGDI and EPOS supports ongoing availability beyond the CRM-geothermal project.
- Hosting agreements at partner institutions (notably University of Miskolc and GFZ Data Services) provide technical continuity.
- Open science compliance ensures that data will remain accessible to researchers, industry, and policymakers even after the project funding period.

7.4 ADDED VALUE OF SUSTAINABILITY

The combination of open access, continuous updates, and integration with European infrastructures transforms the CRM-geothermal database into an enduring scientific and industrial resource. Beyond its role in the project, it will serve as a reference point for future geothermal exploration, CRM recovery initiatives, and raw materials policy development.

8 CONCLUSIONS

Deliverable D1.2 marks a key milestone in the CRM-geothermal project by publishing the CRM-geothermal database as an open, harmonised, and sustainable resource. Building on the work presented in D1.1 and the project’s periodic reports, the database now integrates both legacy datasets from literature and earlier projects (e.g. REFLECT, PERFORM) and new datasets generated through systematic sampling, laboratory analysis, and experimental studies.

The CRM-geothermal database is available both as a continuously updated online resource and as a DOI-based data publication representing a fixed snapshot of the dataset. The publication process has been guided by the FAIR data principles, ensuring that all datasets are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. International metadata standards and open licensing (CC-BY 4.0) have been applied, while persistent identifiers (DOIs) guarantee long-term traceability and citability. The technical implementation, through the online platform and its integration with the Fluid Atlas, provides user-friendly access, visualisation, and export functions.

A continuous workflow has been established for data validation, harmonisation, and integration, enabling newly generated results to be added to the database throughout the project. This ensures that the online database remains dynamic, current, and relevant, while the data publication provides a stable and citable reference version. Interoperability with European data infrastructures (EGDI, EPOS) and links to legacy projects further extend the impact and sustainability of the CRM-geothermal database.

The open publication of the database provides clear benefits:

- For science, it offers a transparent and high-quality dataset to advance geochemical, geological, and technological research.
- For industry, it provides reliable information for innovation in geothermal energy production and CRM recovery.
- For policymakers, it delivers evidence-based data to support strategies on critical raw materials and sustainable resource management.

In conclusion, the CRM-geothermal database transforms a heterogeneous collection of data into a coherent, open, and sustainable resource. It serves as the foundation for the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and will continue to support research, innovation, and policy beyond the lifetime of the project, contributing to the wider European open data ecosystem.

Key achievements in the development of the CRM-geothermal database:

- Integration of legacy datasets from literature and previous projects with newly generated project data.
- Publication of the database in line with FAIR data principles.
- Application of international metadata standards, harmonised vocabularies, and open access licensing (CC-BY 4.0).
- Publication of the database as a DOI-assigned data publication ensuring long-term accessibility and citability.
- Launch of a dedicated online platform with search, visualisation, and export functionalities.
- Establishment of a continuous workflow for data validation, harmonisation, and integration of new results.
- Ensured interoperability with European infrastructures (EGDI, EPOS) and legacy projects (REFLECT, PERFORM).
- Delivery of a sustainable, open, and dynamic resource supporting science, industry, and policy.

9 REFERENCES

Seres, A., Hartai, É., Tompa, T., Szabó, M (2024).; The Horizon Europe CRM- geothermal project: Deliverable 1.1 - Report on data obtained from literature review and existing databases included in the CRM-geothermal database, Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10057307

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Kieling, K., Regenspurg, S. and the CRM-geothermal project consortium (2025): The Horizon Europe CRM-geothermal project: Technical Periodic Report 2, June 2025, GFZ Helmholtz-Centre for Geosciences.

ANNEX 1 — METADATA SCHEMA

Metadata schema for the publication of CRM-geothermal database from GFZ Data Services metadata sheet (<https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/panmetaworks/metaedit/>)

DataCite Metadata

Resource Information

DOI (will be generated in the publishing process)				Year
Resource Type	Title	Version	Language of dataset	
Dataset	CRM-Geothermal Fluid Atlas dataset	v 1.0	en	

Licenses and Rights

Licence	↕
CC BY 4.0	↕

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						↕

Descriptions

Type	Description	↕
Abstract	The data are the background database of the CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas. The dataset was generated by the HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-06 project CRM-geothermal (Raw materials from geothermal fluids: occurrence, enrichment, extraction). CRM-geothermal proposes the combined extraction of heat and Critical Raw Materials from geothermal wells, with maximum returns on investment, minimum environmental impact, requiring no additional land use, leaving no mining legacies, having near-zero carbon footprint, and enabling domestic supplies of CRM. The aim of the CRM-geothermal database and the joining Fluid Atlas is to provide geo-researchers and other, interdisciplinary researchers with a harmonized, high-quality data on geothermal fluids, gases, rocks, and scales, to help decision makers to assess what kind of fluids might be expected at a certain location, and thus have an improved view of the associated risks when installing a geothermal power plant or a plant for example for lithium extraction, to empower local communities and civil society by increasing transparency and public trust by making scientific data openly accessible and easy to explore. Data has been collected from 25 countries, covering most of Europe and East-Africa. It includes detailed information on wells, fluids, rocks, gas and scale, with a special emphasis on critical raw materials. Data comes from former projects: scientific articles, technical descriptions and now data has also been added by analysing fluids, rocks, gases and scales, sampled during the projects.	↕

Thesaurus Keywords (Choose at least one keyword from each thesaurus)

Keyword	Scheme	Scheme URI	Language
EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH > ROCKS/MINERALS/CRYSTALS > ELEMENTS > TRACE ELEMENTS	NASA/GCMD E...	http://gcmdservi...	en
EARTH SCIENCE > SOLID EARTH > GEOCHEMISTRY	NASA/GCMD E...	http://gcmdservi...	en
EARTH SCIENCE > HUMAN DIMENSIONS > ECONOMIC RESOURCES > ENERGY PRODUCTION/USE > GEOTHERMAL ENERGY PRODU...	NASA/GCMD E...	http://gcmdservi...	en
energy > energy type > non-conventional energy > geothermal energy	GEMET	http://www.eione...	en

Free Keywords (Supply as many keywords as you want)

Keyword

fluid properties

geothermal energy

critical raw materials

CRM

Temporal and Spatial Coverage (The EDIT-symbol to the left provides visual selection via Google Maps.)

	Latitude		Longitude		Description of spatial and tempoaral coverage	Date/Time Start		Date/Time End		Time zone
	Min	Max	Min	Max		Date	Time	Date	Time	
	-15.93533	65.8849	-61.7730	44.2832	Europe and East-Africa					

Dates

	Date from	Date to
Created	2025-09-05	
Embargo until		2025-09-20
Valid	1846-01-01	2025-09-30

Related Work

Relation	↑	Type	Identifier
Cites		DOI	https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.3.1.2024.001
Cites		DOI	https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.DMJQ.2025.001
Cites		DOI	https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.3.1.2024.011
Cites		DOI	https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.3.1.2024.003

FundingReference

Funder	Funder ID	Funder ID Type	Grant Number	Grant Name
European Commission	http://dx.doi.org/10.13039/501100000780	Crossref Funder ID	101058163	HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-06

ANNEX 2: THE CRM-GEOTHERMAL DATABASE PLATFORM

This annex presents the CRM-geothermal online database platform, focusing on its interface, structure, and main functionalities as illustrated by a series of screenshots. It provides an overview of how different types of users — from public visitors to registered contributors and administrators — can interact with the system within the database environment.

The description covers the main elements of the user interface, including the navigation bar, the structure of the database tables (wells, fluids, rocks, gases, and scales), and the organisation of records and attributes. It also demonstrates core user actions such as viewing, adding, editing, and deleting data, together with the user access rules applied to these operations.

Further sections illustrate the available search functions (general and advanced search), selection tools, and options for importing and exporting data using the standard Excel template. The screenshots and explanations are limited to the database interface and its data management functionalities. The Fluid Atlas visualisation module is not included here, as it is presented in a separate deliverable

Top navigation bar

1. Database: switch to the Database view here
2. Map: switch to the Map view here
3. *User management: adding or deleting users or changing their role is possible here. Accessible only to administrators.*
4. *User profile: checking and modifying username, name, institution and email address. Available to registered users and admins.*
5. Login/logout: login is only possible after registration from one of the administrators with the e-mails indicated above.

General structure, layout

6. Well, fluid, rock, gas and scale data on different sheets
7. Attributes of the data
8. List of wells, fluids, etc
9. ID of fluid, rock, gas or scale, belonging the given well. Clicking on it takes you to the chosen fluid, rock, etc data.
10. Number of wells, fluids, etc by page

Data management

11. View data: Data of the selected well, fluid, gas, rock or scale in a view window. The small globe icon shows the location of the selected well. Figure 2., 3.
12. *Edit data: Data of the selected well, fluid, gas, rock or scale in an edit window. Here you can modify any data, but only in case it is data you uploaded yourself. Administrators can modify any data. The small globe icon shows the location of the selected well to help ensure the coordinates are correct. Available to registered users and admins. Figure 4.*
13. *Delete data: Deletes the selected data. Registered users can only delete (or edit) the data uploaded by themselves. Admins can delete any data. Deleting a well deletes all the corresponding fluids, rocks, gases and scales.*

Well Data
✕

Basic Info ^

Well ID:	W_AT_001
Local ID:	Blumau 2
Country:	Austria
Facility Name:	
Well Type:	Production well
Latitude:	47.12°
Longitude:	16.04°
Date Of Well Completion:	
Power Thermal:	-

Depth & Elevation ^

Well Head Elevation:	-
Surface Elevation:	-
True Vertical Well Depth:	-
Measured Well Depth:	2843 m

Figure 2. Data view window for wells

Country: Austria
Country code: AT
Latitude: 48.17
Longitude: 14.04

OK

Figure 3. Location check with the globe icon

Well Data

Well ID: W_AT_009

Local ID for well*
Tiefbohrung Wels

Well type

Name of the facility

Date of well completion

Power

Country*
Austria

Latitude*
48.17 °

Longitude*
14.04 °

Wellhead elevation

True vertical well depth

Top of screened interval

Top of screened interval

Surface elevation

Measured well depth

Bottom of screened interval

Bottom of screened interval

Hydraulic head

PZ data

PZ data depth

Bottomhole temperature

Outflow temperature

Well yield

Scaling exists

Depth of measured bottomhole t

Year of outflow temp. measurem

Year of well yield measurem

Inhibitor added

References for the data
Carlé W. (1975): Die Mineral- und Thermalwässer von M

Remarks
well possibly deeper. bottomhole temperature estimated

Figure 4. Data editor window for wells

Search options, selections

14. General search: free-text search. It searches for the typed characters in the whole dataset of the active sheet. E.g. if the Well sheet is active, the search will be conducted in the whole well sheet, it does not have to be related to any attribute, but the search will not run for the other sheets
15. Advanced search: searches for the values of each attribute. More than one search criteria can be added from different sheets. In this latter case there is "AND" relation between the different criteria. Figure 5.
16. Checkmark for selecting data in case more wells, fluids, rocks, gases or scales need to be deleted or exported at once
17. Select all/Select none: Select all: Selects all items on the active sheet. If no search was made, this means all wells, fluids, etc. If a search was conducted previously, select all selects the result of the search. Select none: clears selection. You can remove all checkmarks from the active sheet (well, fluid, rock, etc)
18. Delete selected: deletes the selected rows (marked with a checkmark). In case a well is deleted, the corresponding fluids, rocks, gases and scales are also deleted.

Sample	Attribute	Operator	Value	Value
Well	Outflow Temperature	greater than	70	
Well	Well Yield	greater than	100	
Fluid	Li	greater than	50	
		equals		

Figure 5. Advanced search of CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas and Database tool

Data import/export

19. Add new well/fluid/rock/gas/scale sample: A new item can be added and the data typed in through the data edit window. Fields marked with red are mandatory. Available to registered users and admins. Figure 6.

20. Choose file to import: Adding new data is possible in two ways. One is typing the data directly into the tool through the tool's data edit interface, see in previous point. The other option is importing it from an excel file with this button. In order to successfully upload the data, it has to be in the official CRM-geothermal excel template, available for download from <https://crm-geothermal.eu/>.

21. Export: You can export selected data into xlsx format.

22. Appendix: You can download the files:

- CRM-geothermal Fluid Atlas User Guide
- Guidelines for Data Collection
- CRM-geothermal data Collection Template

Well Data

Well ID * format: W_HU_002	Name of the facility	Country*	
Local ID for well*	Date of well completion year	Latitude*	
Well type	Power MWth	Longitude*	

Wellhead elevation asl	True vertical well depth m	Top of screened interval m	Top of screened interval m
Surface elevation asl	Measured well depth m	Bottom of screened interval m	Bottom of screened interval m
Hydraulic head asl	PZ data MPa/	PZ data depth m	

Bottomhole temperature °C	Outflow temperature °C	Well yield m³/	Scaling exists
Depth of measured bottomhole temp m	Year of outflow temp. measurement year	Year of well yield measurement year	Inhibitor added
	Remarks on well yield measurement	Geothermal gradient in °C/100m	

References for the data	Remarks
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Save data Cancel

Figure 6. Add new data window for wells. Fields marked with red are mandatory